

KPIs to Measure Impact of Technology Projects in the UN 2030 Education Agenda

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Abstract

The development of projects in engineering education often faces the challenge of accurately measuring their impact, particularly in social development. This article introduces a set of KPIs designed to overcome this challenge, which will allow data collection via indicators and the proposal of views to monitor the impact and performance of project solutions on organizations. The study is based on a sample of three projects that took place at UnB, Brasília, in the realm of international cooperation and aiming towards the United Nations 2030 Agenda. The research process consists of three phases: identifying indicators to measure the impact of projects on global societies, determining the necessary data requirements for the indicators, and creating a dashboard to showcase project impact results. This research will help provide data for future projects to be carried out through the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) methodology and in the context of the UN SDG- sustainable development goals. The tool will be integrated into the Unified Platform for Active Methodologies (PUMA), a project conducted at UnB, aimed at evaluating and improving the PjBL methodology within engineering course projects.

Keywords: 2030 Agenda; Project Based Learning; Indicators; Impact of Social Results.

1 Introduction

From the United Nations 2030 Agenda, a global action plan to eradicate poverty through sustainable development, it is possible to explore the role that educational projects in engineering can play in aligning with these global goals. This proposal gains importance with the UNESCO guideline (2019) on Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), which aims to empower students with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes necessary to make informed choices and act responsibly in environmental, economic, and social contexts. However, as highlighted by Neves et al. (2024, p. 163), "to promote a better understanding of sustainability issues, ESD needs to incorporate methods that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and active student participation".

Thus, Problem-based Learning (PBL) and Project-based Learning (PjBL) have emerged as effective methods that transcend traditional education, promoting more interactive and practical learning. Studies show that these methods not only improve students' academic outcomes but also equip them with skills to solve complex problems and make effective decisions in real professional environments (Powell; Weenk, 2003; Savin; Howell, 2004; Graaff; Kolmos, 2007; Chen and Du, 2021).

However, as ESD is integrated into engineering curricula, one of the main challenges in implementing these approaches is the accurate assessment of projects' impacts. The complexity of quantifying social outcomes demands innovative tools that can collect and analyse data effectively. KPI dashboards are a promising tool

that allows detailed monitoring of the performance and impact of projects both in the training of engineering students, and in professional use in organizations in general.

The aim of this work is to develop and implement indicators that can measure the impact of engineering education projects on society, based on active learning approaches, as PBL, and by using a sample of projects conducted at the University of Brasília. This tool aims to provide a database that can be used to continuously improve educational projects in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This paper is organized as follows: initially, a theoretical background and the methodology used to develop the impact indicators are presented. Then, examples of these indicators' application are provided. Through this proposal, it is possible to offer a view of how engineering education projects can be aligned with the principles of sustainable development from the 2030 Agenda.

2 Background

This section introduces theoretical concepts that underpin the research.

2.1 PBL Approaches

According to Šmitiņa and Margeviča-Grinberga (2021), students prefer active, interactive teaching and learning methods which require active engagement, responsibility, problem-solving, decision-making, and self-assessment. Additionally, as noted by AbdelSattar & Labib (2019), active learning has several advantages in engineering education. For instance, it enhances student outcomes compared to traditional methods, their ability to solve open-ended problems, and their general knowledge.

As asserted by Chen and Du (2021), Problem-Based Learning (PBL) constitutes an active learning approach wherein students collaborate in small groups to solve open-ended, real-life problems through self-directed learning. The authors highlight PBL's widespread adoption in engineering education owing to its anticipated advantages in enhancing students' academic performance and transferable skills. Among the benefits of implementing PBL in engineering education is its effectiveness in preparing students to address real-world workplace challenges.

As indicated by Sukacké et al. (2022), active learning strategies, such as Project-Based Learning (PjBL), emerge as among the most pertinent and extensively researched approaches for enhancing learning in engineering. PjBL learning environments are characterized by the fundamental principle of engaging students in solving open problems with an interdisciplinary nature, typically within team settings. A key objective of PjBL is the creation of a final product, distinguishing it from other methods. PjBL often shares commonalities with problem-based learning, as both strategies emphasize collaboration and self-direction. However, the primary distinction lies in the fact that PjBL activities more closely resemble professional tasks.

2.2 Sustainability in Projects

The concept of sustainability is related to a process of transformation in which the use of resources, investment allocation, technological development direction, and institutional changes are aligned with both present and future requirements, according to Khalifeh, Farrell & Al-edenat (2020).

Sustainability comprises three pillars, as shown in Figure 1, the environmental, economic, and social pillars known as the triple bottom line (TBL).

Laedre, Haavaldsen, Bohne, Kallaos & Lohne (2015) recommend that when an investment project is evaluated in terms of sustainability, it should involve assessing its impact on the three pillars: environmental, economic, and social.

By ensuring good practices in indicator development, consulting users may select appropriate indicators. Regular updates and reporting of these indicators offer clear signals regarding the success or failure of national policy initiatives and actions, as mentioned by Dahl (2012).

Figure 1. Key questions of the pillars of sustainability. (Adapted from Keeble, Topiol & Berkeley, 2003)

Indicators must align with the business realities, values, and culture of the organization. Therefore, their development should not be restricted to predefined methodologies or standards (Keeble, Topiol & Berkeley, 2003). These authors suggest a method for evaluating performance at operational levels, such as among projects themselves, where direct environmental, social, and economic impacts are observed. They exemplify this approach with a case study showcasing how businesses can create a suitable set of indicators at two specific levels within the organization: the corporate level and the project level.

To measure a project's impact, it is important to understand which indicators are more suitable for the organization's context. For example, at a corporate level, social responsibility is needed to deliver "sustainable economic, environmental, and social value to organization's extended stakeholders and society in general" (Fonseca et al, 2021). Plenty of social impact and sustainability indicators were created to track, analyze, and certify projects and organizations. Business Corporate certification, for example, is based on a Business Impact Assessment (BIA) to measure and manage a company's positive impact on its workers, community, customers, and environment, both at the operational and business model levels. The assessment covers 5 main aspects of an organization, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Impact Assessment general criteria.

Criteria	Main Topics
Governance	Adoption of a social or environmental mission, ethics, accountability, and transparency Engagement with employees, board members, community, and customers Diversity of governing bodies
Workers	Compensation, benefits, training, and ownership opportunities Work environment, communication, health and safety, career development and job flexibility Worker ownership and engagement
Community	Supplier relations, diversity, and involvement in the local community, for example, community service and charitable giving Whether a company's product or service is designed to solve a social issue

Environment	Environmental management, products, and services Emissions, water, waste Resource preservation Energy efficiency Suppliers and transportation Impacts on climate, water, land, and life Whether a company's products or services are designed to solve an environmental issue
Customers	Company impact on its customers, namely whether its products or services promote public benefit and if those products/services are targeted towards serving underserved populations Whether a company's product or service is designed to solve a social or environmental issue

Adapted from Fonseca et al (2021)

Regarding the PBL methodology in project disciplines, it is difficult to implement it successfully because “learners often lack the self-regulation skills required to monitor, reflect, manage and assess their project activities and learning. Furthermore, most learning systems rarely offer possibilities to monitor and reflect on their project and learning processes.” (Michel et al, 2017). However, there are possible indicators to measure the success of PBL approaches from different perspectives. Traverso-Ribón et al (2016), for example, propose a set of 3 criteria for learning assessment in a PBL experience: the balanced allocation of tasks to the different project roles (C1), the use of tools of the software forge (C2) and the accomplishment of tasks and milestones on time (C3). Table 2 shows which metrics were used to assess each criterion.

Table 2. Metrics used for each criterion.

Criteria	Metrics	Description
C1	Teamwork balance	Standard deviation of number of tickets assigned to each team member
	Leadership	User who created more tickets
	Resolutive capability	User who solved more tickets
C2	Planning creations	Maximum number of days between consecutive ticket creations
	Planning updates	Maximum number of days between consecutive ticket updates
	Version control	Maximum number of days between consecutive commits
C3	Deadline fulfillment	Average delay in the completion of milestones

Adapted from Traverso-Ribón et al (2016)

Michel et al (2017), on the other hand, propose not a set of indicators for PBL projects, but a platform that helps students to manage their activities, in which they can create and manage customizable indicators. A personalized dashboard is then generated, so students and teachers can easily track the projects’ progress and evaluate what’s relevant to them. It is important that the platform provides a guideline for the creation of indicators, to assure that they are S.M.A.R.T. (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Timely). Dashboards are a visual way to analyze data and indicators and can be built into different software, such as Microsoft Excel/Google Sheets, Power BI, Looker Studio, Tableau, etc. But they have to be built strategically, otherwise they may not be useful. According to Michael K. Allio (2012), “a strategic dashboard is one that homes in on the key metrics that reflect progress in implementing strategy. Its primary value lies in its ability to focus senior executive attention, provoke analysis and reflection, and trigger decision-making that improves performance.” The author has created a requirements checklist for a good dashboard, as seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Strategic Dashboard Checklist.

Dimension	Description
Metrics	Indicators/metrics are tightly aligned with strategy, prioritized, and balanced
Audience	It is clear to the whole organization who the dashboard is designed for, and how it's used
Data Capacity	Data collection, infrastructure, analysis, and management are well-developed/organized
Stakeholders	Involved key staff and stakeholders in metrics design & progress reporting
Design	Succinct, accessible display; management judgment was included

Process	There is a formalized key dashboard process: when it's updated, presented, modified
Accountability	The responsibility for managing dashboard content and processes was assigned to one or more members
Effectiveness	Members of the organization used the dashboard to trigger strategic analysis, discussion, and decision-making

Adapted from Allio (2012)

For projects aiming towards the United Nations 2030 Agenda, it is crucial to analyze their impacts, especially on the lens of sustainability indicators.

2.3 Sustainability Impact Indicators of Projects

The questions that underlie the pillars of sustainability, triple bottom line (TBL), are described in Figure 1.

The sustainability indicators of projects can be assessed on a scale of 1 to 5, where a score 1 indicates weak alignment with the principles of sustainable development, and a score 5 indicates strong alignment with the principles of sustainable development. Here are three categories of indicators extracted from the literature (Table 4).

Table 4. Sustainability indicators according to pillars of sustainability.

Economic Sustainability Indicators (ESI)
ROI (Return on Investment)
Financial benefits arising from environmental and social practice
Impact on the local economy
Social Sustainability Indicators (SSI)
SROI (Social Return on Investment)
Number of benefited communities
Number of actions that benefit society
Environmental Sustainability Indicators (EnSI)
Percentage of projects that generate results in eco-efficiency
Percentage of projects that generate results in energy efficiency
Percentage of projects that focus on renewable energy sources
Percentage of projects that aim to reduce the use of natural resources
Percentage of projects that use Recycling and Reuse of products
Percentage of projects that focus on reverse logistics

Adapted from Topiol & Berkeley (2003); Stanitsas & Leopoulos (2021)

These guidelines will be useful for the creation of projects KPIs proposed in this article.

3 Methodology

This research takes an applied approach, aiming to propose indicators for assessing the initiatives of sustainability projects and their impact on society. It employs an exploratory method, sourcing proposed indicators from existing literature for data compilation. Moreover, it has a qualitative focus, prioritizing the presentation of a prototype of indicators for impact assessment rather than variable measurement.

The study's framework comprises three stages. Firstly, it involves identifying indicators to measure the impact of projects on sustainability, aligning with the SDGs. Subsequently, the second stage entails the development of a form for assessing these indicators, while the final stage focuses on creating a prototype that illustrates the project's adherence to sustainability principles.

4 Indicators for International Sustainability Projects

The literature review on sustainable project indicators supported the proposal of indicators for the creation of a dashboard that can be used in the evaluation of projects within the context of an international partnership. This partnership takes place among two universities: the University of Brasília, Brazil and Aalborg University, Denmark. Each semester, an international event called SDG Challenge is held, involving professors and students from each institution. The outcome of this event is a project plan to be executed throughout the semester, focusing on solid waste management and recyclable materials cooperatives. With the project plan and the definition of the scope of each discipline, each partner university develops the project with its students. The question arises: How can the impact of the results of each of the projects developed by the students be assessed? To address this question, a set of indicators is proposed that can be measured based on the results of the deliverables. Table 5 presents the indicators.

Table 5. Sustainability Indicators for the SDG Challenge Project Portfolio.

Indicators	Description	Calculation measures
1. Project Key Management Indicators (PKMI)		
1.1 Scope compliance index	How well the solution delivered represented what was planned	% of actual deliveries vs. planned deliveries
1.2 Technical feasibility of the proposed solution	Validation of stakeholders regarding the proposed solution	Score from 0 to 100%
1.3 Solution applicability index	How applicable the delivered solution proved to be	Score from 0 to 100%
2. Learning Indicators (LI)		
2.1 Student engagement index	How engaged the student was with the project	Score from 0 to 100%
2.2 Learning level	Student evolution in technical and transversal skills	Score from 0 to 100%
3. Economic Sustainability Indicators (ESI)		
3.1 VPL - NPV	Net present value	R\$
3.2 TIR	Internal Rate of Return	% per year
3.3 Payback	Return on investment	Time (years and months)
4. Social Sustainability Indicators (SSI)		
4.1 Index of benefited waste pickers	Number of waste pickers benefited by the project	Number
4.2 Satisfaction index with the solution	Collectors' satisfaction with the proposed solution	Score from 0 to 100%
5. Environmental Sustainability Indicators (EnSI)		
5.1 Index of adherence of the solution to the SDGs	Adherence of the solution to the SDGs	Score from 0 to 100%

Adpted from Topiol & Berkeley, 2003; Stanitsas & Kirytopoulos (2021)

The KPIs proposed in Table 5 can be applied in a context of collaborative projects, within the international partnership of the SDG Challenge project, and they can measure all pillars of sustainability, whether economic, social and environmental.

Project management aims to assess whether the scope of the projects has been met, whether the proposed solution presents technical feasibility through validation with stakeholders, and whether the proposed solution has practical applicability. Indicators of economic sustainability are related to the return on investment, that is, in addition to presenting a solution, the student must be able to demonstrate that this solution is economically

viable, as demonstrated by the Net Present Value (NPV) indices, Internal Rate Return (IRR) and Payback. Social sustainability indicators concern the number of collectors/waste pickers benefiting and how satisfied they are with the proposed solution, as it will impact their workplace within the cooperative, or their personal life. Regarding environmental sustainability indicators, it is necessary to observe the adherence of the solution proposed by students to the SDGs, through a list of questions linked to each SDG and which must be applied to each specific project. This list of questions to assess a project's adherence to the SDGs is a delivery of a product from a project being developed this semester by the international partnership.

It is important to highlight that one of the focuses of the international partnership is to increase the level of student learning. This can be measured by the student's evolution at the beginning of the project and at the end, in relation to technical and transversal skills. The student engagement index can be measured by the level of collaboration between students from different universities, and participating in online meetings during the semester with the exchange of information between projects is one way to evaluate this engagement. Aspects such as cultural differences denote a great experience for students, and dealing with the resolution of real problems related to solid waste and collectors of recyclable materials add to the search for solutions to social problems.

Within the presented proposal, during the 2023 semester it was possible to gather Project Key Management Indicators (PKMI) indicators in three projects within the context of the international partnership. These projects were assessed by two supervising professors, who examined the following: i) Fundraising, which facilitated event planning, content support material, management and indicators; ii) Sustainability Hub, which assessed users journeys of the sustainability hub application; and iii) PUMA Sustainable Impact Module, that allowed a study of the SDGs and their respective impacts on projects. These projects were evaluated in three aspects:

1. Scope compliance index: all planned deliveries and actual deliveries were verified through PM Canvas.
2. Solution applicability index: evaluated by using a Likert scale, ranging from 0 representing not applicable at all to 100 representing highly applicable.
3. Technical feasibility of the proposed solution: also evaluated by using a Likert scale, ranging from 0 representing not applicable at all to 100 representing highly applicable.

This evaluation enabled the creation of a preliminary dashboard, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 displays a dashboard with Project Key Management Indicators (PKMI) for three projects titled Fundraising, Sustainability Hub, and PUMA Sustainable Impact Module developed in the Production System Project 5 (PSP5) course of the Production Engineering program at the University of Brasília. It is important to notice that the projects have not been developed yet. They will be subject to evaluation in the following semester by other PSPs student's teams. All projects demonstrated good performance in the scope compliance index, indicating that the planned deliverables were achieved as expected. Regarding the feasibility of the proposed solution and technical viability, the Fundraising project and the PUMA Sustainable Impact Module proved to be applicable and technically feasible, according to stakeholders' perspectives. However, the Sustainability Hub project showed technical feasibility but did not demonstrate applicability in its solution. These results underscore the importance of evaluating not only scope compliance related to project delivery but also technical viability and practical applicability. It is worth emphasizing the importance of measuring other indicators related to sustainability and student learning level to ensure the success of proposed solutions in future projects.

Proposed Indicators for International Sustainability Projects

Figure 2. Project Key Management Indicators (PKMI) dashboard.

The results depicted in Figure 2 illustrate the collection of project indicators (item 1 in Table 5) due to the absence of a dedicated tool for gathering indicators related to learning levels and sustainability. To address this, we propose the implementation of a data collection tool for use by students at the project's conclusion. This will facilitate the calculation of all indicators outlined in Table 5. Additionally, this tool is integrated with Looker Studio, which will generate dashboard visualizations, enhancing the evaluation and measurement of the project's impacts on sustainability and learning outcomes.

5 Conclusion

Problem-based learning projects on the realm of Education for Sustainable Development also meets the need for key performance indicators, in order to help measure the projects capability to attain certain levels of expectation among stakeholders. This paper has presented how these indicators may be proposed and applied, both for projects evaluation issues as well as how they can impact the real world issues such as the UN 2030 education agenda.

Thus, we have presented some general-purpose project impact indicators that can be suitable for the context of organizations, such as governance, workers, community, environment itself and customers. Other indicators used in PBL approaches are also available to foster this approach of providing specific KPI of the sustainability-related education projects, such as: teamwork balance, leadership, resolute capability, planning creations and updates, version control and deadline fulfillment. The state of the art has showed that by taking these approaches as reference, one may think how projects can be measured under the premises of sustainability.

We proposed in this paper the use of 9 indicators that can be applied to assess the impact of collaborative projects. These projects are the result of a PBL and PjBL approach at the University of Brasília in the context of

the SDG Challenge with the participation of other international institutions. The indicators were gathered into 5 categories as follows: 1. Project key management indicators are scope compliance index, technical feasibility of the solution, solution applicability index; 2. Learning indicators are student engagement index and learning level; 3. Economic sustainability indicators which were based on economic viability and return of investment are VPL-NPV, TIR and payback; 4. Social sustainability indicators are index of benefited stakeholders and satisfaction with the solution and finally 5. Environmental sustainability indicators is the index of adherence of the solution to the SDGs.

These indicators were then applied in the course of a 2023 semester, and projects were evaluated under the aspect of scope compliance index, solution applicability index as well as technical feasibility of the solution. The analysis conducted with the use of indicators showed that all projects attained 100% of scope compliance. The solution applicability index was highly achieved by one project, but not achieved by the others. Technical viability was also high in all three projects analysis. Therefore, we also concluded that it is possible to focus on the impact of projects in sustainability and to withdraw conclusions about their social relevance and financial feasibility with the use of these indicators. We understand the limits of the present analysis and the need to validate the results in a wider range number of projects as well as in other areas where sustainability is important. The next steps of this approach are to conduct a broader analysis considering all the proposed indicators in order to evaluate their application and efficiency.

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6 References

- AbdelSattar, A., & Labib, W. (2019). Active learning in engineering education: Teaching strategies and methods of overcoming challenges. *In Proceedings of the 2019 8th International Conference on Educational and Information Technology* (pp. 255-261).
- Allio, M. K. (2012). Strategic dashboards: designing and deploying them to improve implementation. *Strategy & Leadership*, 40(5), 4-13.
- Chen, J., Kolmos, A., & Du, X. (2021). Forms of implementation and challenges of PBL in engineering education: a review of literature. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 46(1), 90-115.
- Dahl, A. L. (2012). Achievements and gaps in indicators for sustainability. *Ecological Indicators* 14-19.
- Fonseca, L., Silva, V., Sá, J. C., Lima, V., Santos, G., & Silva, R. (2021). B Corp versus ISO 9001 and 14001 certifications: Aligned, or alternative paths, towards sustainable development? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 1-13.
- GRAAFF, E.; KOLMOS, A. (2007). *Management of change: implementation of problem-based and project-based learning in engineering*, Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Khalifeh, A. Farrell, P. & Al-edenat, M. (2020). The impact of project sustainability management (PSM) on project success. A systematic literature review. *Journal of Management Development*. vol. 39 no. 4. pp. 453-474.
- Keeble, J. J.; Topiol, S. & Berkeley, S. (2003). Using Indicators to Measure Sustainability Performance at a Corporate and Project Level. *Journal of Business Ethics* 44: 149-158.
- Laedre, O.; Haavaldsen, T.; Bohne, R. A.; Kallaos, J. & Lohne J. (2015). Determining sustainability impact assessment indicators. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*. vol. 33, No. 2, 98-107.
- Michel, C., Lavoué, E., George, S., & Ji, M. (2017). Supporting Awareness and Self-Regulation In Project-Based Learning through Personalized Dashboards. *International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 9(2/3), 204-226.
- Neto, G. M. P.; Alencar, L. H.; Rabbani, E. R. K. & Valdes-Vasquez, R. (2021). An Analysis of Social Sustainability Indicators Using FITradeoff Multicriteria Decision Method. *IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)* | 978-1-6654-3771-4/21.
- Neves, R. M.; Shayani, R. A.; Viana, D. M.; et al. (2024). Aprendizagem ativa para além da sala de aula: Preparando estudantes de engenharia para construir um mundo mais justo e sustentável. In: Adriana Maria Tonini e Tânia Regina Dias Silva Pereira. (Org.). *Abenge 50 Anos: Desafios de ensino, pesquisa e extensão na educação em engenharia*. 1ed. Brasília: Abenge. 159-211.
- Powell, P. C.; Weenk, W. (2003). *Project-led engineering education*. Utrecht: Lemma Publishers.
- Savin-Baden, M.; H, M. C. (2004). *Foundations of problem-based learning*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Stanitsas, M.; Kirytopoulos, K.; Leopoulos, V. (2021). Integrating Sustainability indicators into project management: the case of construction industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 279 (2021) 123774.

- Stanitsas, M.; Kirytopoulos, K. (2021). Investigating the significance of sustainability indicators for promoting sustainable construction project management. *International Journal of Construction Management*. Vol. 23, no 3, 434-448.
- Traverso-Ribón, I., Balderas-Alberico, A., Doderó, J., Ruiz-Rube, I., & Palomo-Duarte, M. (2016). Open data framework for sustainable assessment of project-based learning experiences. *Program: electronic library and information systems*, 50(4), 380-398.
- UNESCO (2019), Framework for *the implementation of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) beyond 2019*. Available at: <<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000370215>>. Accessed on April 12, 2024.